

Qualitative Study on Impact of Da'awah and Zakat in Islam: Panacea for Social Security and Poverty Eradication in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper titled qualitative study on impact of da'wah and Zakat in Islam: panacea for social security and poverty eradication in Nigeria examines the kind of attitude most Nigerian present. It is extremely unfortunate that many Muslims have decided to abandon this pillar in favor of micro-credit models that are based on riba (usury). Hence, little do those Muslims realize that their Islam cannot remain intact if they deny a pillar or they make permissible that which is actually impermissible. The aim of the paper therefore, is to convey the position of Islam to the rich who have well to do in assisting their fellow Muslim brothers as the foundation of the society of love and brotherhood includes cooperation, mutual compassion and support, not only that the paper seeks to show the view of religion of Islam which shows that the Qur'an, the service of humanity and the amelioration of the condition of the poor has always been among the principal aims and objects of religion. The paper adopts a survey and historical research methodology, it reviews aspects of da'wah such as its definition, commands Prophets serving as models for perfection in conveying the message of Allah (SWT) encouraging the Ummah to give zakat among others. It was concluded that poverty is a disease that threatens belief, faith, morals conduct, thought, culture, the family, society, and the Ummah in general, because it takes away man's dignity and extinguishes his pride, saps his energy and robs him of the opportunity to succeed. And then recommended that man should bear in mind that Allah is the creator of the universe, man and wealth, as regards to wealth is a trust, that all the rich have to respond to the command of Allah and give this right to the people who are entitled to it.

Key Words: Da'wah, Poverty, Eradication, Zakat, Social, Security,

Introduction

In the Muslim society there may be people who are unable to work, and who have no well-off relatives who can spend on them. What can these poor and weak people do? What can the needy that are unable to work do, such as orphans and widows, the elderly, the mentally and physically handicapped, the blind and the sick? These people are not forgotten in the Muslim Ummah (society) that is guided by Islam. They have the right to Zakah, and they are the first ones on whom it should be spent (Muhammad 2007). Islam does not deny an individual his rights or hold back from helping him, supporting him and ensuring that he is granted his right. Islam calls for a society where there is no oppression of the poor by the rich and no hatred of the rich by the poor, because the rich man in the Muslim society is generous and acknowledges the rights of the poor over his wealth. The country, which was one of the richest countries in the early 1970s, has retrogressed to become one of the 25 poorest countries at the threshold of the twenty first century (Bambale 2020). It is to be understood that all things belongs to Allah, and wealth is therefore hold by human being in trust. The original meaning of the word zakat is both purification and growth (Ibrahim1997). Giving Zakat means giving a specified percentage on certain properties to certain classes of needy people. The percentage which is due on gold, silver, and cash funds that have reached the amount of 85 grams of gold and held in possession for one lunar year is two and a half percent. An individual's possession is purified by setting aside a small portion for those in need, and like the pruning of plants, this cutting back balances and encourage new growth. A person may also give as much as he or she pleases as voluntary alms or charity.

The word Zakat is the infinitive noun of the verb: Zakat meaning: to grow or to increase or to be pure in the heart. The literal meaning of Zakat, therefore, is growing, increasing; or purification of the heart. (al-Jarir 1999)

But in Islamic Law, Zakat takes a different meaning from the one known to the Arabs before the coming of Islam. The Prophet (saw) defined Zakat as what is taken out of the property of the rich ones and given to the poor ones. That is why the learned scholars said: Zakat is a portion of a person's wealth, which is the right of Allah, given to the poor people. (al-Qardawi 1977)

Zakat is the second pillar of Islam, by means of which Allah guarantees the poor and needy a share of the wealth of the ummah and the state, and it is often mentioned in conjunction with Prayer in the Qur'an and Sunnah. It is mentioned in 28 places in the book of Allah (SWT). It is an ancient form of worship that has always existed in the one religion of Allah that was preached (Da'wah) by all the Prophets and Messengers, until the advent of Islam which is the final religion of Allah.

In Islam being an act of worship, Zakat also became a new and unique system which no previous divinely –revealed religion or earthly law had ever prescribed. Zakat is one of the five pillars of Islam which Islam made compulsory by Allah (SWT) in the Qur'an. The bases of which Zakat is given can be trace from the Glorious Qur'an where Allah (SWT) said to His Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and some Prophets (R.A) before him viz:

خُذْ مِنْ أَمْوَالِهِمْ صَدَقَةً تُطَهِّرُهُمْ وَتُزَكِّيهِمْ بِهَا وَصَلِّ عَلَيْهِمْ إِنَّ صَلَاتَكَ سَكَنٌ لَهُمْ وَاللَّهُ سَمِيعٌ عَلِيمٌ

Take Sadaqah from their wealth in order to purify them and sanctify them with it, and Salli for them. Verily, your Salat are a Sakan for them; and Allah is All-Hearer, All-Knower. (Q.9:103)

The above verse is teaching the Muslim Ummah that giving Zakat cleans the Ummah from impurity of meanness, greed, misery and lack of showing mercy to the poor. Allah (SWT) commanded His Messenger to take Sadaqah from the Muslims' money to purify and sanctify them with it. This Ayah is general, even though some said that it refers specifically to those who mixed good and evil deeds, who admitted to their errors.

In another verse of the Glorious Qur'an Allah (SWT) ordered the believers to give out from the legal property and the good things they produce in their farms. The verse in other words, is teaching the Ummah that Allah (SWT) will accept only what is legally earned, it reads:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ ءَامَنُوا أَنْفِقُوا مِنْ طَيِّبَاتِ مَا كَسَبْتُمْ وَمِمَّا أَخْرَجْنَا لَكُمْ مِنَ الْأَرْضِ وَلَا تَيَمَّمُوا الْخَبِيثَ مِنْهُ تُنْفِقُونَ وَلَسْتُمْ بِأَخْذِيهِ إِلَّا أَنْ تُغْمِضُوا فِيهِ وَاعْلَمُوا أَنَّ اللَّهَ غَنِيٌّ حَمِيدٌ

O you who believe! Spend of the good things which you have (legally) earned, and of that which We have produced from the earth for you, and do not aim at that which is bad to spend from it, (though) you would not accept it save if you close your eyes and tolerate therein. And know that Allah is Rich (free of all needs), and worthy of all praise. (Q.2:267)

According to Ibn `Abbas, in Ibn Kathir (1999) Allah (SWT) commanded the believers to spend from the purest, finest and best types of their money and prohibited spending from evil and dishonest money, because Allah is pure and good and only accepts that which is pure and good." This is why Allah said,

وَلَا تَيَمَّمُوا الْخَبِيثَ

and do not aim at that which is ba

An understanding of the phrase above indicates that, Muslims should know that whatever one manages to acquire of worldly goods, income, money and sustenance throughout one's life time should not be filthy (impure).

Some bedouin later thought that paying Zakah to the Leader was not legislated except to the Messenger himself, using this part of the Ayah as evidence. Abu Bakr As-Siddiq the first successor of the Prophet (SAW) and other Companions (RA) refuted this ill comprehension and fought against them until they paid the Zakah to the Khalifah, just as they used to pay it to the Messenger of Allah. As-Siddiq said:

"By Allah! If they abstain from paying a bridle that they used to pay to the Messenger of Allah, I will fight them for refraining from paying it (Bukhari book of zakat:705)

Allah's statement,

وَصَلِّ عَلَيْهِمْ

and Salli for them,

According to ibn Kasir (1999) the above phrase means, supplicate for them, and ask Allah to forgive them. In the Sahih, Muslim recorded that `Abdullah bin Abi Awfa said, "Whenever the Prophet was brought charity, he used to invoke Allah for those who brought it. My father also brought his charity and the Prophet said:

«اللَّهُمَّ صَلِّ عَلَى آلِ أَبِي أَوْفَى»

O Allah! I invoke You for the family of Abu Awfa)"

Allah (SWT) said

﴿أَلَمْ يَعْلَمُوا أَنَّ اللَّهَ هُوَ يَقْبَلُ التَّوْبَةَ عَنْ عِبَادِهِ وَيَأْخُذُ الصَّدَقَاتِ﴾

Know they not that Allah accepts repentance from His servants and accepts the Sadaqat)

This Ayah encourages reverting to repentance and giving charity, for each of these actions erases deletes and eradicate sins. Allah states that He accepts the repentance of those who repent to Him, as well as charity from pure resources, for Allah accepts it with His Right Hand and raises it for its giver until even a date becomes as large as Mount Uhud. Abu Hurayrah narrated that the Messenger of Allah said,

إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَقْبَلُ الصَّدَقَةَ وَيَأْخُذُهَا بِيَمِينِهِ فَيُرَبِّبُهَا لِأَحَدِكُمْ كَمَا يُرَبِّي أَحَدَكُمْ مَهْرَهُ، حَتَّىٰ إِنِ الثَّقَمَةَ لَتَكُونُ مِثْلَ أُحُدٍ

Verily, Allah accepts charity, receives it in His Right Hand and develops it for its giver, just as one of you raises his pony, until the bite of food becomes as large as Uhud. Hadith,

"*Da'wah*", is an Arabic word literally means 'to call', 'to summon', 'to invite.' And 'ask to come' (Wehr, 1980). The first two meanings of "*Da'wah*" worshipping and calling are frequent in the Qur'an, "*Da'wah*" and its derivatives are used in different contexts in its literal and technical meanings. Since in the Qur'an the word "*Da'wah*" appears numerous times, only those verses that speak of or imply the preaching and spreading of Islam are dealt with in the present paper.:

Da'wah is a way by which the Muslims are made to understand Islam better while the non- Muslims are exposed to the beauty of Islam and are shown the natural way to their Creator Allah (S.W. T). The Prophet (S.A.W) instructed Muslims to do the same as he was commanded. He said:

"وليبغ الشاهد الغائب" رواه البخارى

Shouldn't the one present among you convey (the knowledge) to those who are absent. (Bukhari Vol. 1, 104)

In another way, it is the responsibility of Muslims to guide people, admonish the Ummah to pay Zakat and show them the way to Allah (SWT). Such people who handle the work of *Da'wah* are the successors of the Prophet (S.A.W) for their engagement on the essential mission of the Prophet (S.A.W) who was entrusted with the task of *Da'wah*.

Islam has therefore, obliged every conscious and serious-minded Muslim to use all available and lawful means of communication to spread the message of Islam to all people, preaching through speeches as well as through the pen is highly encouraged in the Islamic tradition. In writing, local as well as international languages must be used to keep the Ummah informed on the issue of Zakat collection and distribution to the rightful beneficiaries so as to eradicate poverty.

Ordering goods and forbidding the bad which are ordained by the Qur'an charging the Messengers of Allah with the responsibility to disseminate the revealed guidance with which they were entrusted, their respective nations too, were called upon to share in the fulfillment of Allah's orders which is fard'ayn.

The word "*Da'wah*" however, is not the only Arabic word that describes "calling". "*Nida*" is also an Arabic word, which means "to call". This term or its derivatives are also used in the Glorious Qur'an which is used to mean "inviting people to faith the Qur'an reads:

Our Lord, indeed we have heard a caller [i.e., Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) calling to faith, [saying], 'Believe in your Lord,' and we have believed. Our Lord, so forgive us our sins and remove from us our misdeeds, and cause us to die with the righteous. (Q3:193)

Other Arabic synonyms for "*Da'wah*" with "*nida*" being the most common of Muslim *Du'at* activities, is the term "*Tabligh*" an Arabic word used for, "conveyance". to "fulfill" or "implement" a mission, that is, to cause or bring about a given task, or to convey successfully a specific message which is an active requirement, *Amr-bil-ma'roofwanahyi anil-munkar*(enjoining the good and forbidding the evil). The Qur'an reads:

And let there be [arising] from you a nation inviting to [all that is] good, enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong, and those will be the successful. (Q. 3:104)

The doctrine of *Da'wah* is linked with the doctrine of *Amr-bil-ma'roofwanahyi anil-munkar*(enjoining the good and forbidding the evil). The two are identical in the sense that Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and the Muslims have never been asked by Allah to invite people to Islam itself but to the Truth, to enjoin good and forbid evil, which, in fact, Islam is, and thus lead people to accept Islam as the embodiment of the Truth.

Baidawi (1840), subscribes to the position that "enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong" is a collective activity and explains it by saying that not all would be capable of fulfilling the duty of "enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong" the duty of "enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong" is a fardkifaya.

Jalal al-Din (2008) notes that "the task which has been placed on the shoulders of the Ummah by Allah, the Almighty is expressed in this glorious verse in two terms; the first of them is calling to excellence and the second is enjoining the good and forbidding the evil." His observation also suggests that there should be a group of concerned Muslims who would be charged with a double task: *Da'wah* through knowledge plus practical action.

In another verse of the Glorious Qur'an Allah (SWT) instructed the Prophet (SAW) thus:

Say, this is my way - I invite unto the God with clear evidence, I and whoever follows me (Q.12:108),

Call to Allah as used in the above verse meant call to His religion, and that is Islam. Indeed, the religion of Allah is Islam which Prophet Muhammad (SAW) brought from his Lord. And Islam is the object of *Da'wah*. And indeed, you invite them to a straight path. It invites he who turned his back (on truth) (from obedience)

, Prophet Ya'qub (As) said to his people:

I convey unto you the Messages of my Lord, and I am a trustworthy adviser for you (Q.7:68)

According to *Al-Mahaly* and *As-Soyuty* (1431/2010) these means I am worthy of being trusted with the message with which I am sent to you, for I am a well-wisher for you. In another submission, he said:

My advice will not profit you ever if I wish to give you good counsel, if Allah's will be to keep you astray. He is your Lord! And to Him you shall return. (Q.11:34)

The following terminologies expatiate the concept of *Da'wah*.to has included the following terms: *Shahadah* (witness), *Nasihah* (advice or counsel), *Tabshir* (glad tidings or good news), *Inzaar* (warning), *Tadhkir* (reminding) people about their obligations and duties such as paying the *zakat* which promotes their wellbeing and their status. The Qur'an states:

Therefore, remind in case the reminder profits. (Q87:9)

Meaning, remind where reminding is beneficial. From here we get the etiquette of spreading knowledge, that it should not be wasted upon those who are not suitable or worthy of it. The Commander of the believers, 'Ali said, "You do not tell people any statement that their intellects do not grasp except that it will be a *Fitnah* (trial) for some of them." He also said, "Tell people that which they know. Would you like for Allah and His Messenger to be rejected" Allah said:

سَيَذَكَّرُ مَنْ يَخْشَى

The reminder will be received by him, who fears, (Q87:10)

Meaning, 'he whose heart fears Allah and knows that he is going to meet Him, will receive admonition from what you convey to him, O Muhammad, 'it is therefore, only those who fear Allah (SWT) and are certain that they will meet their lord in the hereafter and will be accountable of all actions that will make use of the admonition of the Du'at and practice their teachings in alleviating the poverty of their fellow Muslim brother.

Hujjah which means concluding the argument, and conveying the message in full.

We sent Messengers as bringers of good tidings and warners; so that mankind will have no argument against Allah after the Messengers. And ever is Allah Exalted in Might and Wise. (Q.4:165)

It is in the light of all these terms that *Shafi'i* (1997) pointed out toward certain important dimensions of *Da'wah* viz:

1. Inviting people to accept the divinely revealed truth and to follow the truth prescribed by Allah (S.W.T);
2. Witnessing or testifying in favor of the divine truth before people who either do not know or have not accepted it;
3. Manifestation or explanation of truth before mankind through words and deeds;
4. Advising or preaching people to obey the commands of Allah (SWT) and to defy the evil dictates of all the evil forces including *Satan* and wicked rulers, governments, group parties and also one's own deviant self;
5. Propagating the message of truth among mankind
6. Giving people glad tidings about the positive result of embracing truth in this world and in the next
7. Warning and cautioning people against both the immediate and remote consequences of rejecting or even neglecting the divine guidance;
8. Reminding people of the forgotten realities that success in this life and salvation in the hereafter can be achieved only by accepting and following the way of life prescribed by Allah (S.W.T) and;
9. Conveying the message of truth to such an extent that any person who is indifferent towards this message should not be able to take shelter under the excuse that he was ignorant of this message.

Da'wah which connotes admonishing the Ummah on all aspects of life of a believer has a role to play in admonishing the rich to give from their wealth to the poor and the needy. This order was given almost to all prophets and messengers of Allah long before the time of Muhammad (SAW). For example, Allah says, praising the father of the Prophets Ibrahim, and Ishaq and Yaqub:

وَجَعَلْنَاهُمْ أئِمَّةً يَهْتَدُونَ بِأَمْرِنَا وَأَوْحَيْنَا إِلَيْهِمْ فِعْلَ الْخَيْرَاتِ وَإِقَامَ الصَّلَاةِ وَإِيتَاءَ الزَّكَاةِ وَكَانُوا لَنَا عَابِدِينَ

And We made them leaders, guiding by Our command, and We revealed to them the doing of good deeds, performing *Salah*, and the giving of *Zakah*, and of Us (Alone) they were the worshippers. (Q.21:73)

And he says praising Ismail: and he said to his family and his people prayers and zakat and his lord was pleased with him:

وَأَذْكُرُ فِي الْكِتَابِ إِسْمَاعِيلَ إِنَّهُ كَانَ صَادِقَ الْوَعْدِ وَكَانَ رَسُولًا نَبِيًّا - وَكَانَ يَأْمُرُ أَهْلَهُ بِالصَّلَاةِ وَالزَّكَاةِ وَكَانَ عِنْدَ رَبِّهِ مَرْضِيًّا

And mention in the Book, Isma'il. Verily, he was true to what he promised, and he was a Messenger, (and) a Prophet. And he would enjoin on his family and his people the Salah and the Zakah, and his Lord was pleased with him. (q.19:54-55)

In another place in the Glorious Qur'an Allah (SWT) said in addressing Prophet Musa (AS): And my mercy embraces all things. That (Mercy) I shall ordain for those who are muttaqun (the pious), and give zakat; and those who believe in Our Ayat (proofs, evidences, verses, lessons, signs and revelations, etc (Q.7:156)

In addition, Allah (SWT) tells us that Prophet Isah (as) said speaking from the cradle: And He has made me blessed wheresoever I am, and has enjoined on me prayers and Zakat as long as I live (Q.19:31)

Allah (SWT) commanded the children of Israel: And speak good to people (ie) enjoin righteousness and forbid evil and say the truth about Muhammad and establish prayer and give zakat (Q.2:83)

And He said concerning the people of the book: And they were commanded not, but that they should worship Allah, and worship none but Him Alone (abstaining from ascribing partners to Him), establish prayers and give Zakat, and that is the right religion. (Q.98:5)

Islam denounces poverty and regards it as a disease that threatens the belief, faith, morals and culture. Islamic legislation provided so many steps to do away with poverty, example when it comes to religious feelings and moral guidance there are many texts of the Qur'an and Sunnah which touch the heart of the rich Muslim and tap a sprig of generosity and kindness, so that he gives abundantly to the poor.

Zakat has far reaching effects which we are only beginning to understand and appreciate. Economist have speculated that if everyone paid the required Zakat every year, poverty could soon be eradicated from the world, (Sherman 2012) . He further illustrated that by paying the Zakat to the poor and the needy a fairer share of the world's money and resources, thereby increasing their buying power and providing them with opportunities they might not have had.

Zakat further lessens the animosity the poor feel towards the rich, but it is considered a right of the poor, not a favor bestowed upon them. It is such an important command that Allah has threaten to hold back rain if it is not carried out. The Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said if people abstain from paying Zakat they would be deprived of rain (In Majah)

Islam made Zakah as a foundation or means of social security, as it is made both as an act of worship and a systematic form of tax on wealth which guarantee the right of the poor and is not simply an act of kindness or voluntary charity. Zakat is to be collected by the Muslim state, which will appoint full-time workers to collect it, these workers are to be given a share of the zakah funds to ensure that it is collected independently of other kinds of wealth to be collected by the state, and so that it will not be mixed with other kind of wealth, thus causing the right of the poor to be lost. (Q.9:60)

It is sufficient to know that the one who withholds Zakah may be fought and his blood may be shade until he pays it in full as prescribed in the rulings of Islam. The words of caliph Abubakar (R.A) concerning the apostates who withhold Zakah still ethos through history, where he declared thus: By Allah I will certainly fight those who separate prayer and Zakat (Ibn kathir 1989)

Some people think that Zakah can only be given to the poor who have nothing at all. This is not correct. Rather it may be given to that type of poor people or it may be given to those who have some of what they need, but who do not have enough.

إِنَّمَا الصَّدَقَتُ لِلْفُقَرَاءِ وَالْمَسْكِينِ وَالْعَمِلِينَ عَلَيْهَا وَالْمَوْلَفَةَ قُلُوبُهُمْ وَفِي الرِّقَابِ وَالْغَرَمِينَ وَفِي سَبِيلِ اللَّهِ وَابْنِ السَّبِيلِ فَرِيضَةً مِّنَ اللَّهِ وَاللَّهُ عَلِيمٌ حَكِيمٌ

As-Sadaqat (i.e., Zakah) are only for the Fuqara', and Al-Masakin and those employed to collect (the funds); and to attract the hearts of those who have been inclined (towards Islam); and to free the captives; and for those in debt; and for Allah's cause, and for Ibn As-Sabil; a duty imposed by Allah. And Allah is All-Knower, All-Wise. (Q. 9:60)

Abu Hurayrah narrated that the Messenger of Allah peace be upon him once said:

«لَيْسَ الْمَسْكِينُ بِهَذَا الطَّوَّافِ الَّذِي يَطُوفُ عَلَى النَّاسِ فَنَزِدُهُ الْقُمَّةَ وَاللَّقَمَتَانَ، وَالنَّمْرَةَ وَالنَّمْرَتَانَ»

قالوا: فمن المسكين يا رسول الله؟ قال

«الَّذِي لَا يَجِدُ غَنًى يُغْنِيهِ، وَلَا يُفْطِنُ لَهُ فَيُتَصَدَّقَ عَلَيْهِ، وَلَا يَسْأَلُ النَّاسَ شَيْئًا»

The needy person is not the one who goes round the people and asks them for a mouthful or two (of meals or a date or two). They asked, "Then who is the needy person, O Allah's Messenger!" He said, (The one who does not have enough to satisfy his needs and whose condition is not known to others, that others may give him something in charity, and who does not beg of people. (Bukhari and Muslim)

An understanding of the Hadith above shows that a poor person is not he who walks around among people looking for something to eat and who is driven away by (being given) a few mouthfuls or a few dates. Rather, a poor person is he who does not have enough money to live on and is not known to people as needing charity, and it is he who does not walk around asking people for charity.

One of the most prominent features that distinguish the Muslim society from other societies is its mutual support, brotherhood and solidarity. There is no oppression of the poor by the rich and no hatred of the rich by the poor, because the rich man in the Muslim society is generous and acknowledge the rights of the poor over his wealth, so he does not deny him his right or hold back from helping him, supporting him, and ensuring that he is granted his right by the rich (Muhammad 2007)

Islam therefore, allows for the ownership of property i.e. wealth but has set some guidelines on the basis of which wealth circulates. These guidelines include zakat. On reaching certain prescribed amount and duration, a person is expected to give a certain percentage of his hard-earned money to the poor by whom their economic position is raised and improved. The poor in an Islamic state is not strangled by the capitalist or communist. He has a chance of improving his condition to the extent of becoming also wealth. Instead of receiving the zakat he gives it out from his fortune.

Within a short period of time, if Zakat is constantly given out it will reach a time when everyone will become affluent and stand not in need of any assistance from anybody. History has shown during the time of Umar bn Abdulaziz one of the Ummayyads Caliphs that not a single person entitles to the Zakat could be at a certain point found. If this is so then it is one of the objectives of Zakat not only to raise the economic position of the poor, but also to eradicate poverty among people. Refusal to pay zakat, there are rich people nowadays, who owned millions and billions, if they were to pay the zakat on this wealth it will be sufficient to eradicate poverty from society totally, let alone what could be achieve if they were to spend generously of their wealth. These rich people are too stingy even to pay zakat even though they know that it is an obligatory duty and is one of the pillars of Islam.

The government neglects this duty and does not collect and distribute the zakat, then those in authority who rule according to the Islamic Sharia and well-informed Islamic organization if the members are just, pious and do fear Allah are to collect it are solely responsible.

As individuals are left to their discretion to give out to the destitute only few God-fearing ones give it out while many others avoid it or even delaying payment of zakat (Lawal 2020)

People so much love the wealth for their children than to themselves that is they prefer their children to inherit them instead of spending in the cause of Allah (SWT). Once the Prophet (SAW) said: Is there anyone among you whose heir's wealth is dearer to him than his own wealth?" They said, "O Messenger of Allah, there is no one among us but his own wealth is dearer to him." He said, His wealth is that which he has sent (by giving charity before he passes away), and his heir's wealth is that which he has left behind (Bukhari)

Transfer of Zakat from one town to another is permissible according to the sayings of the majority Scholars where there are pressing needs, that is if the beneficiaries are more in that area. Muhammad (2007)

In a hadith the prophet (SAW) sent Muadh bin Jabal to Yemen when he said to him:

إِنَّكَ تَأْتِي قَوْمًا مِنْ أَهْلِ الْكِتَابِ، فَلْيَكُنْ أَوَّلَ مَا تَدْعُوهُمْ إِلَيْهِ شَهَادَةً أَنْ لَا إِلَهَ إِلَّا اللَّهُ - " وفي رواية: إلى أن يوحدوا الله - " فإن هم أطاعوك لذلك فأعلمهم أن الله افترض عليهم خمس صلوات في كل يوم وليلة، فإن هم أطاعوك لذلك فأعلمهم أن الله افترض عليهم صدقة تؤخذ من أغنيائهم وترد على فقرائهم، فإن هم أطاعوك لذلك فإياك وكرائم أموالهم، واتق دعوة المظلوم، فإنه ليس بينها وبين الله حجاب.

You are going to people of the book. First of all, invite them to worship Allah (Alone); and when They come to know Allah, inform them that Allah Has Enjoined on the five prayers in every day and night; and if they start offering these prayers, inform them that Allah has enjoined on them; the Zakat. And it is to be taken from the rich amongst them and given to the poor amongst them; and if They obey you in that, take Zakat from them and Avoid (don't take) the best property of the people As Zakat, (Bukhari, 2/537)

Way Forward on Adequate Payment of Zakat in Nigeria

Callers (conveyers of Allah's message are to educate and encourage the Muslim Ummah on the position of Islam on those who refuse to give Zakat and the punishment that awaits them in the hereafter, Abu Hurayrah reported that the messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) said:

“He whom Allah (SWT) has given wealth and who does not give Zakat will meet on the day of judgment monstrous old, bald male snake which will encircle him and grab his lips saying I am your wealth. I am your treasure.” (Bukhari)

It is the duty of the Duat to admonish the general populace of the Muslim Ummah to out Zakat out of the good things which Allah has provided them with to this effect Abu Hurayrah reported that the Prophet (SAW) said: ” He who gives as alms what may equals to a date - provided that it is earned legally, since Allah (SWT) only accepts what is good-will be granted Allah’s acceptance of it. Likewise, for him who raises a foal, Allah will raise this charity for him until it becomes as big as a mountain (Bukhari)

Whoever gives charity equal in value to a date, from good (Hala) earnings for Allah does not accept anything but that which is good Allah will take it in His right hand, then he will look after it just as any one of you looks after a foal when it is first born, until it becomes like a mountain. Once the Prophet (SAW) said Is there anyone among you whose heirs wealth is dearer to him than his own wealth? “They said, “O’ Messenger of Allah, there is no one among us but his own wealth is dearer to him.” He said, His wealth is that which he has sent on ahead by giving charity before he passes away, and his heir’s wealth is that which he has left behind (Bukhari), There should be a force (Islamic authority) to enforce its collection and distribution at whatever cost should the giver refuse to give it out

Conclusion

From the forgone discussions one can rightly conclude that poverty is a disease that threatens belief, faith, morals conduct, thought, culture, the family, society, and the Ummah in general, because it takes away man’s dignity and extinguishes his pride, saps his energy and robs him of the opportunity to succeed. Thus, the Messenger of Allah use to seek refuge from poverty to the extent likened it to kufr in the following Hadith “oh Allah, I seek refuge with You from disbelief and poverty” Man, whom Allah has appointed as his vicegerent and trustee in this world, to develop it with guidance, goodness, virtue and righteous deeds to benefit the people, cannot fulfil this mission in life when he is restricted by poverty. The wealth retained by two percent of the world’s wealthiest individual could completely eliminate poverty from the entire world. Since there are many Muslims who are extremely wealthy, it is not difficult to gauge the impact that zakah could have on global poverty.

Recommendations

It is recommended therefore, that:

1. Mankind should bear in mind that all wealth belongs to Allah (SWT) and man is only a vicegerent of Allah;
2. Allah (SWT) created it and gave it to His slaves. The rich man is appointed in charge of it and he is entrusted with it;
3. Man is to spend it (wealth) and to dispose of it well, and to develop it in accordance with the command of Allah, so as to earn His pleasure;
4. Zakat should be given to the rightful beneficiaries only so as to eradicate poverty among Muslim Ummah.

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